
A SURVEY OF FISH FAUNA OF LOWER OGUN RIVER AT ISHASI, OGUN STATE,
WESTERN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

A survey was carried out on species composition, abundance and seasonal distributions of fish fauna in Ishasi area of Lower Ogun River from January 2006 to December 2007. Fish samples were collected using cast net and drop traps on monthly basis from three stations (stations 1, 2 and 3). Relative uniform distribution of fish fauna was observed as fish abundance and diversity levels recorded from the three stations were not significantly different ($p>0.05$). A total of 1419 specimens of fish of forty-three species and seventeen families were collected with Margalef species richness and Shanon-Wiener diversity indices values of 7.79 and 2.76 respectively. *Barboides gracilis* of Cyprinidae family dominated the fish species with relative abundance of 21.42% followed by *Tilapia zilli*, a Cichlid (12.36%) and *Aphyosemion gulare*, a Cyprinodontid (9.66%). Species collected also included endangered single-species-in-the-family such as *Lates niloticus* (Centropomidae) and *Heterotis niloticus* (Osteoglossidae). In term of family, Cichlidae was the dominant with seven species representation followed by Characidae with five species. The rainy season had higher fish total abundance (1061), species number (38), and diversity levels than dry season when a total abundance of 358 and 25 species were recorded. The imperativeness of sustainable management and conservation of the fish resources in Lower Ogun River is discussed.

KEYWORDS: Fish fauna, Composition, Distribution, Abundance, Lower Ogun River, Sustainable management.

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria is blessed with numerous natural water bodies with abundant fish resources. Nigerian fresh water bodies are the richest in West Africa in terms of fish abundance and (Olaosebikan and Raji, 1998; Idodo-Umeh, 2003; Meye and Ikomi, 2008). The fish resources, apart from being a major source of high quality animal protein for man, provide several other socio-economic values such as sources of job opportunity and raw materials for some industrial activities as well as recreational purposes.

Fish occupy high trophic levels of food chains in aquatic ecosystems, thus their composition in a location reflects both the summation of conditions of lower biological forms and the overall water quality (APHA, 1985). Knowledge of compositions and distribution of fish in a water body is therefore very crucial for sustainable exploitation of its fish resources as well as effective management and conservation of the entire aquatic ecosystem.

Ogun River is one of the two principal rivers in the Ogun-Osun River Basin of Nigeria. The river supports a major artisanal fisheries activity especially in the downstream. Recent works on biological characteristics in the lower course of Ogun River include Yakub (2010) and Yakub and Ugwumba (2009) which were mainly focused on macro-invertebrate fauna.

There is dearth of recent information on fish fauna of the lower course of Ogun River. The work of Syndeham (1977) on the qualitative composition and longitudinal zonation of fish fauna of the entire Ogun River has been carried out for a quite long time. It is highly necessary to update existing information on fish fauna of the lower course of the river. This study therefore investigated the composition and distribution of fish fauna in Ishasi area of Lower Ogun River for effective and sustainable management of the fisheries and other resources in the water body.

Study Area

The study was carried out in Ishasi area of Lower Ogun River. The entire study area lies on Longitude $3^{\circ} 16''E$ and Latitude of between $6^{\circ} 40''N$ and $6^{\circ} 41.5''N$ (Fig.1) and has a typical tropical rainforest climatic condition. In the area, rainy season stretches from April through November while dry season lasts from December through March. Especially towards the bank, the river is fringed by different types of macrophytes which include floating higher plants such as duck weed (*Lemma* spp.), water lettuce (*Pistia*) and water hyacin (*Echiorna crassepes*) and rooted plants such as Elephant grass (*Pennisetum*), Giant star grass (*Cynodon*) and Bamboo (*Bambusa*).

Artisanal fishing activities both for finfish and fresh water prawns, *Marobrachium* were the major human activities observed in the study area. The neighbouring community also depends on the river for source of water for domestic use.

Fig. 1: Map of Lower Ogun River showing sampling stations

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection

Fish samples were collected from three stations (1, 2 and 3) at 200m intervals (Fig. 1) on monthly basis from January, 2006 to December, 2007.

Sampling of fish was done using two methods:

(i) Drop trap:- Conical shaped drop traps (1m long and 40cm diameter) with funnel-like non-returning mouth and double inner chambers were used for fish capture. The traps were baited with cassava and trash fish.

At each sampling station, a trap was set at a shallow area of each of the left and right banks of the river by submerging the trap into water with the mouth facing downstream. The traps were tethered to a stick firmly in the river bottom. The traps were left for 24 hours for fish capture. The fish captured were retrieved by loosening the trap at the tapered bottom end and emptied into a plastic container.

(ii) Cast net:- Three random throws with cast net of 75mm mesh size and 5m diameter were made within the mid-channel area of the river at each station for fish collection.

Fish samples collected with the trap and cast net were composited as fish fauna sample of each station.

Fish collected at each station were sorted into various species. Identification was done both on the field and in the laboratory using fish identification guides including Reed *et al.* (1976), Olaosebikan and Raji (1998) and Idodo-Umeh (2003).

The number of individuals for each species was counted and recorded.

Data obtained from identification and counting were used to compute fish compositions, distributions and abundance for each station as well as for the entire study area (pooled data of the three stations). Relative abundance of every taxa for the entire study area was also computed. Also, Simpson's Dominance (C), Margalef species richness diversity (d) and shanon-Wiener (H) indices levels of fauna of each station as well as for the entire study area were computed as described by Ogbeibu (2005) using a computer software package, 'Past' by Hammer and Harper (2005). Diversity levels of the three stations were compared also with the software package.

Fish abundance levels of the three stations were compared, using 'ANOVA-Two Factor Without Replication' (Ogbeibu, 2005) under Microsoft Excel. For seasonal composition and distribution of fish fauna, data obtained in the months of April to November in 2006 and 2007 were pooled for rainy season while the pooled data of the months of January to March and December, 2006 and 2007 were used for dry season.

RESULTS

Stations 1, 2 and 3 had thirty-five, twenty-eight, and thirty-five fish species respectively. Spatial distribution of community structure of fish fauna of the study area is presented in Table 1. The fish species recorded belonged to sixteen, fourteen and fifteen families at stations 1, 2 and 3 respectively (Table 1). The three stations had comparable species richness (d) values as well as insignificantly different Shanon diversity (H) and monthly fish abundance values (Table 1).

In the entire study area, Cichlidae had the highest representation (seven species) followed by Charachidae with five species. Table 2 presents various fish taxa, relative abundance of every taxa and the diversity indices values recorded in each of the rainy and dry seasons. Each of Cyprinodontidae, Mastacembelidae, Osteoglossidae, Clupeidae and Centropomidae had one species representation (Table 2)

Barboides gracilis of Cyprinidae family was the dominant fish taxon with the highest relative abundance (22.34% and 18.99% in rainy and dry season respectively) followed by *Tilapia zilli*. Other fish species with high relative abundance in rainy season were *Aphyosemion gulare* (11.03%), *Brycinus longipinnis* (10.75%) and *Mastacembelus cryptocantus* (8.29%) (Table 2). In the dry season, *Gobius guineensis*, *Eleotrius senegalensis* and *A. gulare* also had relatively high abundance levels (12.85%, 7.54% and 5.60% respectively) (Table 2).

Out of the forty-three fish taxa collected during the study, thirty-eight were recorded in the rainy season while dry season had twenty-five taxa (Table 2). Higher values were also recorded for total number of fish, Margalef species richness index (d) and Shanon diversity index (H) in the rainy than dry season (Table 2).

DISCUSSION

The comparable levels of diversity (d) as well as insignificantly different H and mean abundance in the three stations indicate a relative uniformity in the species distribution, composition and diversity of fish in the entire study area. The uniform fish distributions could be attributed to the uniform physico-chemical conditions and macro-invertebrates which constitute a major group of food organisms for fish in the area as reported by Yakub and Ugwumba (2009).

Fish species encountered in the study encompass the fresh water fish of the families that are of important species diversity such as Mormyridae, Cichlidae, Mochokidae and Cyprinidae (Egborge, 1992; Obasohan and Oronsaye, 2006). The authors also highlighted some species of these families that are of restricted distributions, out of which *Pelvicachromis pulcher*, (Cichlidae), and *Barbus occidentalis* (Cyprinidae) were come across in the present study. However, of all the endangered single-species-in-the-family listed by Obasohan and Oronsanye (2006), only *Lates niloticus*, (Centropomidae) and *Heterotis niloticus* (Osteoglossidae) were encountered.

All species and families of fish encountered in the present study have been reported to occur in Nigerian fresh water bodies by earlier workers such as Reed *et al.* (1967), Olaosebikan and Raji (1998) and Idodo-Umeh (2003). Sydenham (1977) and Olaosebikan and Raji (1998) had earlier reported occurrence and distributions of most of these species in Ogun River. The record of 43 species from 17 families of fish in the present study compares well with 41 species from 28 families recorded by Alfred-Okiya (1996) in Kolo

Creek and that of Meye and Ukomi (2008) that reported 45 species from 24 families in Urie Creek, Niger Delta.

The record of higher fish species and abundance in the rainy than dry season conforms with the findings of some earlier workers but contradicts what was reported by other authors. Perhaps, fish abundance is influenced by different factors in different seasons. Higher fish abundance was recorded in dry than rainy season in Lower Bonny Estuary by Chindah and Osuamkpe (1994), mangrove habitat of Lagos Lagoon by Nwadukwe (1995) and Urie Creek, Niger Delta by Meye and Ikomi (2008). The authors attributed this to the reduced water level, which makes fish collection easier and render the fish more susceptible to catching during dry than rainy season.

On the other hand, higher total fish abundance levels recorded during rainy than dry season in the present study could be due to reproductive activities which for most fish species take place in the rainy season. This could have boosted their populations during the period (Idodo-Umeh, 2003). Bankole (1990) and Allison *et al.*, (2007a) described recruitment as a major source of variability in fish populations. The higher fish abundance in the rainy than dry season recorded in the present study is also attributable to relatively high availability of food in the season. Yakub and Ugwumba (2009) recorded significantly higher macro-invertebrate (a major group of fish food organisms) abundance in the rainy than dry season in the area. Iorchor *et al.* (2007) recorded higher fish abundance in the wet season, though predominantly juveniles than dry season in the main channel of the Lower Benue River. Higher abundance of *Parailia pelucida* during rainy than dry season in the fresh water reaches of Nun River, Niger Delta was also reported by Allison *et al.*, (2007b).

The findings in this study show that Lower Ogun River has great potential to support fisheries activities considering its fairly high species composition and abundance as well as uniform distribution of fish. The seasonal variations in species composition, distribution and abundance should however be put into consideration in the course of exploiting the fish resources. Also, more research activities are advocated especially on ecology of the water body for its effective management. Further studies are also recommended on some other aspects of biology of the relatively dominant species, cultivable ones such as Cichlidae (*Tilapia*), Clariidae (*Clarias* and *Heterobranchus*) and Bagridae (*Chrysichthys*). Those in the list of endangered single-species-in-the-family such as Osteoglossidae (*Heterotis*) and Centropomidae (*Lates niloticus*) need further studies especially on their ecology/biology in order to ensure their conservation.

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Table 1: Spatial Distribution, Diversity and Abundance of Fish Fauna in Lower Ogun River (January 2006-December 2007)

	Station 1	Station 2	Station 3
Total Abundance	439	470	510
Total Number of Taxa	35	28	35
Total Number of Families	16	14	15
Margalef Diversity (d)	5.59	4.39	5.45
Shanon Diversity (H)	2.75 _a	2.69 _a	2.71 _a
Mean Monthly Abundance	31.44±16.72 _a	34.67±17.03 _a	36.73±19.31 _a

a= For each parameter, data in the same row with the same subscript are not significantly different (p>0.05)

Table 2: Composition, Distribution and Diversity of Fish Fauna In Ishasi Area of Lower Ogun River (January 2006-December 2007)

TAXA	ABUNDANCE		
	TOTAL	Rainy Season	Dry Season
Cyprinidae:			
<i>Barboides gracilis</i>	304 (21.42)	236 (22.24)	68 (18.99)
<i>Barbus occidentalis</i>	7 (0.49)	2 (0.19)	5 (1.40)
Cichlidae:			
<i>Tilapia Zlli</i>	174 (12.26)	117 (11.03)	57 (15.92)
<i>T. guineensis</i>	6 (0.42)	3 (0.28)	3 (0.84)
<i>T. mariea</i>	3 (0.21)	1 (0.09)	2 (0.56)
<i>Hemichromis bimaculatus</i>	4 (0.28)	4 (0.38)	-
<i>H. fasciatus</i>	4 (0.28)	4 (0.38)	-
<i>Pelvicachromis pulcher</i>	7 (0.49)	7 (0.66)	-
<i>P. taeniatus</i>	5 (0.35)	-	5 (1.40)
Characidae:			
<i>Brycinus longipinnis</i>	117 (8.25)	114 (10.75)	3 (0.84)
<i>B. leusiscus</i>	25 (1.76)	17 (1.60)	8 (2.23)
<i>B. brevis</i>	14 (0.99)	14 (1.32)	-
<i>Hydrocynus forskal</i>	2 (0.14)	2 (0.19)	-
<i>H. lineatus</i>	1 (0.07)	1 (0.09)	-
Cyprinodontidae:			
<i>Aphyosemion gulare</i>	137 (9.66)	117 (11.03)	20 (5.60)
Schilbeidae:			
<i>Paraetropiusbuffei</i>	48 (3.38)	36 (3.39)	12 (3.35)
<i>Parailia pelucida</i>	35 (2.47)	32 (3.02)	3 (0.84)
<i>Schilbe intermidius</i>	28 (1.97)	28 (2.64)	-
<i>S. mystus</i>	14 (0.99)	13 (1.23)	1 (0.28)
Mastacembelidae:			
<i>Caecomastacembelus cryptocantus</i>	107 (7.57)	88 (8.29)	19 (5.31)
Gobiidae:			
<i>Gobius guineensis</i>	94 (6.62)	48 (4.52)	46 (12.85)
<i>Goboides ansorgii</i>	2 (0.14)	2 (0.19)	-
Eleotridae:			
<i>Eleotris senegalensis</i>	63 (4.44)	36 (3.39)	27 (7.54)
<i>E. vivata</i>	20 (1.40)	13 (1.23)	7 (1.96)
Bagridae:			
<i>Chrysichthys nigrodigitatus</i>	24 (1.69)	22 (2.07)	2 (0.56)
<i>Bagrus dogmac</i>	2 (0.14)	2 (0.19)	-
Mormyridae:			
<i>Marcusenius brucii</i>	16 (1.13)	-	16 (4.47)
<i>M. branchistus</i>	1 (0.07)	1 (0.09)	-
<i>Gnathosenius branchistus</i>	1 (0.07)	1 (0.09)	-
<i>Pollimyrus adsepersus</i>	7 (0.49)	5 (0.47)	2 (0.56)
Mochokidae:			
<i>Synodontis courteti</i>	1 (0.07)	-	1 (0.28)
<i>S. nigrita</i>	7 (0.49)	7 (0.66)	-
<i>S. sorex</i>	4 (0.28)	4 (0.38)	-
Osteoglossidae:			
<i>Heterotis niloticus</i>	11 (0.78)	11 (1.04)	-
Clupeidae:			
<i>Leaviscutella dekimpei</i>	9 (0.63)	9 (0.85)	-
Distichodontidae:			
<i>Neolabias ansorgii</i>	88 (6.2)	52 (4.9)	36 (10.06)
<i>Ichthyoborus monodii</i>	5 (0.35)	2 (0.19)	3 (0.84)
<i>Phago loricatus</i>	11 (0.78)	6 (0.57)	5 (1.40)

NB: Values in parenthesis represent Relative Abundance of every species in each season.

Table 2 Contn.

TAXA	ABUNDANCE		
	Total	Rainy Season	Dry Season
Anabantidae			
<i>Ctenopoma kingsleyae</i>	6 (0.42)	-	6 (1.68)
<i>C. perterici</i>	1 (0.07)	1 (0.09)	-
Centropomidae:			
<i>Lates niloticus</i>	2 (0.14)	2 (0.19)	-
Clariidae:			
<i>Clarias agbyiensis</i>	1 (0.07)	1 (0.09)	-
<i>Heterobranchus isopterus</i>	1 (0.07)	-	1 (0.28)
Total Number of Individuals	1419	1061	358
Total Number of Taxa	43	38	25
Margalef Diversity (d)	7.79	5.31	4.08
Shanon Diversity (H)	2.76	2.70	2.57
Mean Monthly Abundance		115.70	77.13

NB: Values in parenthesis represent Relative Abundance of every species in each season.

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